

Algorithmic Mirror: Interactive Visualizations for Adolescents to Understand and Challenge Algorithmic Profiling in Online Platforms

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Fig. 1. Conceptual illustration of the three platforms, TikTok, YouTube, and Netflix constructing a teen's profile from collected data, visualized as a mirror that reflects algorithmic interpretations of viewing interests.

Social media platforms routinely track and monetize adolescents' data while offering little visibility into how algorithms construct their digital identities. While XAI scholars have sought to reveal the inner workings of algorithms, their approaches frequently overwhelm end-users with technical complexity. We introduce *Algorithmic Mirror*, an interactive visualization tool that transforms opaque profiling practices into explorable landscapes of personal data. It uniquely leverages adolescents' real digital footprints across TikTok, YouTube, and Netflix to provide situated, personalized insights into datafication over time. In our study with 27 participants aged 12 to 16 we show how engaging with their own data enabled adolescents to uncover the scale and persistence of data collection, recognize cross-platform profiling, and critically reflect on algorithmic categorizations of their interests. Our findings show that identity is a powerful motivator for reflecting on the impact of algorithms, highlighting the need for platforms to ensure young people have transparency and control over their algorithmic profiles.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → *Empirical studies in HCI*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Adolescents, Datafication, Reflection, Social Media

1 Introduction

Social media platforms convert adolescents’ everyday interactions into data for algorithmic analysis. This process, known as datafication [29, 31], enables platforms to create detailed digital representations of users’ preferences, shaping personalized content recommendations [26]. Adolescence represents a crucial window of vulnerability to these systems [21]. Teens are sensitive to immediate feedback and social rewards while their critical thinking is still maturing [5, 28]. Yet adolescents lack tools to understand the digital identities constructed from their data, leaving them behind a ‘one-way mirror’ with diminished agency over their online experiences [14, 16].

Researchers have explored tools to foster datafication awareness and critical algorithmic literacy [18, 30]. However, most rely on hypothetical contexts through simulations or synthetic data, disconnected from adolescents’ lived experiences [6, 23]. As a result, insights often remain abstract and difficult to transfer into informed choices about their own digital lives [30].

We propose Algorithmic Mirror, an interactive tool that allows adolescents to visualize their real watch histories from TikTok, YouTube, and Netflix. We conducted a qualitative study with 27 adolescents aged 12–16, who uploaded viewing histories ranging from 100 to 60,000 videos across platforms and up to five years of activity. We investigated how Algorithmic Mirror facilitated adolescents’ reflection on the datafication of their online experience. We show that Algorithmic Mirror makes the scale and scope of datafication visible, fostering reflection on online experiences and critical awareness of algorithmic systems.

2 Algorithmic Mirror

Algorithmic Mirror is an interactive visualization tool for exploring how platforms construct digital identities from viewing data, extending Latent Lab [8]. We identified five design rationales, each operationalized through specific system components.

DR1: Grounding Reflection in Personal Data. Learning is most effective when grounded in lived experience [6, 23]. Participants upload their viewing histories from TikTok, YouTube, and Netflix via each platform’s data export tools. Our preprocessing pipeline enriches exports by retrieving missing metadata (e.g., titles, descriptions) through platform APIs and external databases.

DR2: Surfacing Algorithmic Interpretation. Making algorithmic inference visible supports critical examination of how identity is categorized from behavioral data [7]. The semantic mapping view organizes videos by thematic similarity, with dense regions annotated by topic labels (Figure 2). We generate this layout using text-embedding-ada-002 [19] and UMAP [17], with topics extracted via GPT-4o-mini [20]. Topic labels are embedded in the same space, positioning them near semantically related videos. Through zooming and panning, users explore how their viewing patterns are algorithmically organized (Figure 3).

DR3: Revealing Temporal Persistence. Algorithmic memory persists—past behaviors continue to shape categorization long after they occur [1]. An interactive timeline supports cross-platform temporal exploration (Figure 3). Users observe how their content landscape changes as topics rise and fall—trending content may briefly bubble to prominence, while foundational interests gradually shift toward central positions.

DR4: Exposing Cross-Platform Reach. Profiling extends beyond any single platform through data sharing and aggregation [11]. Platform-level filtering through color-coded selections allows users to compare digital footprints across

3 User Study

We conducted 27 user study sessions (July–September 2025, post-IRB approval) with adolescents aged 12–16 (14 girls, 13 boys; mean age 14.1) across Japan, the UK, and Europe. Prior to sessions, researchers guided participants through downloading personal data from their chosen platforms using official export features; participants then securely uploaded data to Algorithmic Mirror with personal identifying information removed. Participants uploaded data from YouTube (n=22), Netflix (n=11), and TikTok (n=5). Each 60-minute session combined open exploration with think-aloud [9] and semi-structured interviews: warm-up (10 min), free exploration of Algorithmic Mirror (25 min), temporal exploration (15 min), and closing questions on datafication perceptions (10 min). Sessions were video-recorded (949 minutes total) and analyzed through collaborative coding by three researchers.

4 Findings

Seeing their personal data visualized often provoked breakdown moments—surprises or discomforts that disrupted adolescents’ assumptions about algorithmic representation. These breakdowns prompted active inquiry, as participants proposed and tested hypotheses about how platforms collect and infer. Through this process, many experienced transformed awareness and articulated new desires for control.

Breakdown: Encountering the Datafied Self Initial encounters with the Mirror triggered breakdown moments that disrupted assumptions about algorithmic representation. Most participants (22/27) felt accurately represented, while a few (3/27) found labels unsettlingly accurate (“a platform can represent my data more than I know myself” [P18, age 14]) or disconnected from their self-perception (8/27). The temporal visualization surprised many (10/27) in both volume and extent, and almost half (13/27) encountered forgotten content. Participants with multi-platform data discovered different services represented them differently—TikTok emphasized “fashion... storytelling nostalgia” while YouTube showed different content [P27, age 13].

Inquiry: Making Sense of Algorithmic Representation Following breakdowns, participants engaged in active inquiry. By hovering over data points and manipulating the timeline slider, many (17/27) worked to explain why particular content appeared, connecting videos to life events. P22, encountering “reproductive rights” from November 2022, recalled: “Oh yeah, it was when Roe v. Wade was overturned” [P22, age 15]. This process surfaced awareness of identity change (19/27): “My interests changed a lot, especially things like Titans and anime. I don’t watch any of those anymore” [P24, age 15]. Participants also theorized about algorithmic inference, reasoning about demographic profiling (5/27) and developing theories about recommendation mechanisms (13/27).

Transformation: Shifted Awareness and Desires for Control Most participants (22/27) reported transformed awareness of the scope of data collection. P1 described: “I knew the algorithm and that it was there and influencing me, but I didn’t realize that it could be taken and mirrored in such an extent” [P1, age 13]. Some had data extending back to early childhood; P6 reflected: “It feels very surprising to see that they have known me since I was a child” [P6, age 13]. Over half (15/27) described feeling watched: “It’s like a pair of digital eyes spying on you” [P5, age 13]. This transformed awareness generated desires for control. Many (12/27) wanted to limit algorithmic access to sensitive domains, particularly mental health, while others (10/27) sought space to explore new interests without being trapped by past data: “I wanna find something out of that box” [P9, age 14].

5 Discussion

We proposed a new approach to supporting adolescents' reflection on datafication through personalized visualizations of their own data. Algorithmic Mirror enabled adolescents to establish personal connections with their data, fostering self-reflection and motivation for autonomy; recognize the scale and temporal reach of datafication across platforms; and investigate their own questions about their digital traces.

From Data Awareness to Identity Relevance Algorithmic Mirror facilitated identity reflection by leveraging personal data (DR1) and surfacing algorithmic interpretations (DR2). Participants evaluated whether representations were accurate, compared them against who they wanted to be, and felt motivated to shape how they were perceived. Their reflections focused on self-identity rather than datafication itself, seen through their expressions of surprise at platform intimacy, discomfort with mental health inferences, and desire to escape algorithmic boxes. Previous research shows children understand data traces and express desires for autonomy, but desire does not automatically translate into action [15, 30, 32]. These findings suggest a shift from data awareness toward identity relevance as a design principle: activated identity shapes goals and sustains effort toward identity-congruent behaviors [22], enabling adolescents to see algorithmic representations as reflections of who they are and want to become.

From Abstract to Concrete Datafication Algorithmic Mirror makes visible both temporal persistence (DR3) and cross-platform reach (DR4), which are dimensions hidden in everyday interactions. The timeline enabled participants to see datafication as continuous activity rather than isolated snapshots, discovering that platforms retained years of viewing history [3, 12]. The cross-platform visualization surprised participants by revealing how distinct "platform selves" could be stitched into a single profile. Previous tools have visualized single-platform snapshots [10, 30] or server-side data flows [4], but not aggregated views across platforms and time. Integrating both dimensions helps users grasp datafication as continuous, cross-platform surveillance.

From Explanation to Exploration: Designing for Reflective Inquiry Personal data (DR1) combined with open exploration (DR5) created conditions for reflective inquiry—not by explaining algorithms, but by inviting participants to encounter and investigate their own representations. When self-understanding did not match the visualization, this produced breakdown moments that catalyzed reflection [2]. Crucially, Algorithmic Mirror did not tell participants how algorithms work; it let them figure it out themselves. This suggests a reorientation for algorithmic literacy tools from comprehension to inquiry [24, 25]. However, effectiveness depended partly on researcher facilitation; without scaffolding, standalone deployment may yield less depth [13, 27].

6 Conclusion

This research addresses how to empower adolescents with digital autonomy amidst pervasive datafication. We introduced Algorithmic Mirror, a personalized visualization tool that surfaces algorithmic interpretation of years of viewing data across YouTube, TikTok, and Netflix. Our study with 27 adolescents (ages 12–16) suggests that designing for identity relevance can motivate reflection on the impact of algorithms. Key design considerations include: presenting algorithmic interpretation in forms that enable self-recognition, surfacing temporal persistence and cross-platform reach, and enabling exploration where adolescents ask their own questions. When adolescents saw themselves reflected in their data, motivation to act stemmed not from abstract privacy concerns but from personal investment in shaping their algorithmic identities. This suggests that grounding explainability in personal relevance, rather than technical transparency, can make algorithmic systems meaningfully legible to the people most affected by them.

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A Participant information

Table 1. Participant demographics and which platform data they uploaded to Algorithmic Mirror. Where consecutive rows are shaded the same, the participants took part as a group, e.g., P9, P10, and P11 formed one group, P12 and P13 formed another group.

ID	Gender	Age	TikTok	YouTube	Netflix
P1	F	13	×	✓	✓
P2	M	14	✓	✓	✓
P3	M	16	×	×	✓
P4	M	12	×	✓	×
P5	M	13	×	✓	✓
P6	F	13	×	✓	✓
P7	F	14	×	✓	×
P8	F	12	✓	✓	✓
P9	F	15	×	×	✓
P10	F	13	×	✓	×
P11	F	15	×	✓	✓
P12	M	16	×	✓	×
P13	M	15	×	✓	×
P14	M	15	×	✓	×
P15	M	15	×	✓	×
P16	M	14	×	✓	×
P17	M	14	×	✓	×
P18	F	14	×	×	✓
P19	M	14	×	✓	×
P20	F	14	✓	✓	×
P21	M	14	×	✓	×
P22	F	15	×	✓	×
P23	F	15	×	✓	×
P24	F	15	×	×	✓
P25	M	13	×	✓	✓
P26	F	14	✓	×	×
P27	F	13	✓	✓	×